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INSTITUTE OF SOCIAL SCIENCES
DEPARTMENT OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE EDUCATION**

**THE EFFECTS OF COMPUTER MULTIMEDIA LIFE SIMULATION GAMES
IN ENGLISH VOCABULARY LEARNING**

**THESIS BY
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MASTER OF ARTS

MERSİN / OCTOBER 2020

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DEDICATION

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Program : Master Thesis(X) Ph.D. Thesis()

Thesis Title : The Effects of Computer Multimedia Life Simulation Games
in English Vocabulary Learning

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İbrahim Hakkı ERGİN

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15/10/2020

İbrahim Hakkı ERGİN

ABSTRACT**THE EFFECTS OF COMPUTER MULTIMEDIA LIFE SIMULATION GAMES
IN ENGLISH VOCABULARY LEARNING****İbrahim Hakkı ERGİN****Master of Arts, Department of English Language Education****Supervisor: Dr. Ali BIÇKI****October 2020, 60 Pages**

Contributing to language teaching by using computers is an area that has been developing since the 1960s. Computer-assisted language learning (CALL) research, which started with mainframe computers, continues with computers with superior features currently. These enhancements have not only been limited to hardware but have also made significant progress in terms of software. Today, interactive studies are conducted in many areas with the assistance of interactive technology. Some of these studies are related to simulation games. This study aimed to measure the effects of computer multimedia life simulation games on English vocabulary learning and to reveal the positive and negative effects of using simulation games in a classroom environment. Eighteen participants from the prep classes of Mustafa Kemal University participated in the study and two groups were formed as experiment and control group. This experimental study was carried out in a computer laboratory for four weeks and in the light of the data obtained from the pretests and posttests, it was observed that computer multimedia life simulation games had a significant effect on learning English vocabulary. In addition, journal entries and findings from an Implementation Evaluation Questionnaire have revealed some positive and negative consequences of using simulation games in classroom settings.

Key Words: CALL, learning vocabulary, simulation games, computers, language learning

ÖZET**ÇOKLU ORTAM BİLGİSAYAR HAYAT SİMÜLASYON OYUNLARININ
İNGİLİZCE KELİME ÖĞRENİMİNDEKİ ETKİSİ****İbrahim Hakkı ERGİN****Yüksek Lisans Tezi, İngiliz Dili Eğitimi Anabilim Dalı****Tez Danışmanı: Dr. Öğr. Üyesi Ali BIÇKI****Ekim 2020, 60 Sayfa**

Bilgisayarları kullanarak dil öğretimine katkıda bulunma çalışmaları 1960'lardan beri gelişmeye devam eden bir alan. Anaçatı bilgisayarlarla başlayan bilgisayar destekli dil öğrenimi araştırmaları bugünlerde üstün özelliklere sahip bilgisayarlarla devam etmektedir. Bu gelişmeler sadece donanımlarla sınırlı kalmamış, yazılımlar bakımından da kayda değer bir ilerleme kat etmiştir. Bu çalışma bilgisayar çoklu ortam hayat simülasyon oyunlarının İngilizce kelime öğrenimindeki etkisini ölçmek ve simülasyon oyunlarını sınıf ortamında kullanmanın olumlu ve olumsuz etkilerini ortaya çıkarmayı hedeflemiştir. Çalışmaya Mustafa Kemal Üniversitesi hazırlık sınıflarından 18 katılımcı dâhil olmuş, bunlardan deney ve kontrol grubu olmak üzere iki grup oluşturulmuştur. Deneysel olarak yapılan bu çalışma bir bilgisayar laboratuvarında dört hafta boyunca gerçekleştirilmiş ve yapılan öntest ve sontestlerden alınan veriler ışığında, bilgisayar çoklu ortam hayat simülasyon oyunlarının İngilizce kelime öğreniminde anlamlı bir etki oluşturduğu gözlemlenmiştir. Bunlara ilaveten, günlük girişleri ve bir uygulama değerlendirme anketinden elde edilen bulgular, bilgisayar oyunlarının sınıf ortamında kullanılmasının bazı olumlu ve olumsuz sonuçlarını ortaya çıkarmıştır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: CALL, kelime öğrenimi, simülasyon oyunlar, bilgisayarlar, dil öğrenimi

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CHAPTER I

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background Information

Using technology in language teaching is an important research subject today, especially the ones on the effects of computer and mobile games in English language teaching. The history of teaching English with computers started with Computer Assisted Language Learning (CALL) by using simple computers and has evolved throughout time and became what we comprehend now with the production of complex machines. For these complex machines, sophisticated software and hardware were developed and provided opportunities for implementing enhanced activities in classrooms. The development of computers required the advance of commercially produced computer games. Over time, computer games began to contain sound, graphics, and video similar to those in real life. These innovations created a unique opportunity, especially for simulation games. Because the basic purpose of simulation games is to transfer realistic situations to games with minimal loss. The authentic content of these positive features attracted many researchers who wanted to study language learning. To create the links between simulation games and learning settings, there has been some research about these opportunities including multimedia life simulation games such as The Sims (Miller & Hegelheimer, 2006; Noroozloo, Ahmadi, & Mehrdad, 2015; Ranalli, 2008). These studies are based on using interaction and communication while using a complex computer game and demonstrated to us that life simulation games are significantly effective in vocabulary acquisition.

1.2. Statement of the Problem

The students in English Language Teaching department in Mustafa Kemal University do not have adequate chance to apply English in their daily lives and not read materials sufficiently to learn new vocabulary. Additionally, the students mostly cannot mediate their learning because of teacher dependent context. Since this can conflict with their interests, they may not use their full potential in acquiring vocabulary.

1.3. Significance of the Study

This study is of great importance to enable students to become familiar with words and to notice their use in an authentic context by using a more developed game than the games used in previous studies by taking advantage of the suggestions written for further studies. It may contribute to the literature to find out what kind of consequences the advantages and disadvantages that student autonomy can carry. Moreover, the study can contribute to education by providing ideas to instructors and curriculum makers on computer-assisted language teaching to be used in education in Turkey.

1.4. Purpose of the Study

In Turkey, students do not have the chance of using what they learn. This is especially a problem for language teaching. Using computer games which most learners have access to can help them to use the language they learn. It may not be as interactive as speaking with others, yet who have not the chance to use the language may get opportunities to their vocabulary. Thus, the purpose of this study is to find out whether computer multimedia life simulation games have effects in English vocabulary acquisition and to explore the positive and negative outcomes of using computer simulation games in Mustafa Kemal University.

1.5. Research Questions

The following research questions were identified with the intention of achieving the purposes and helping to solve the problems:

- a) Can multimedia life simulation games help students in the acquisition of vocabulary in English?
- b) What are the positive and negative consequences of using a multimedia life simulation game in a classroom setting?

1.6. Limitations

This research was conducted with 18 prep class students at Mustafa Kemal University. The implementation time was four weeks.

CHAPTER II

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2.1. Introduction

Computer applications in second language learning (CASLA) started with plans discovering advance and expenditure of computer assisted language learning (CALL) inside the area of educational technology and was formed by viewpoints in teaching as well as by computer hardware and software upgrading for aims other than language education (Kerr, 2004).

CALL in the 1960s was maintained by mainframe computers linked to stations on a separate campus or by telephone connections to stations off-campus. Computer centered education movements, named “courseware” were progressed applying programming languages and were collected on a mainframe for pupils to access as desired. The mainframe computer and their common-purpose program writing languages of the 1970s were capable to maintain the plain interaction vital to apply the instructional scheme for this era of CALL. Compared with our times’ levels, courseware was not technologically advanced although it was frequently cautiously designed. The truth that the software was collected on a separate mainframe at an institute permitted for log storing in the main place and interaction between users (Chapelle, 2001, pp. 3–4).

In spite of difficulties such as expense, language instructors all over the world were charmed by the possibilities CALL seemed to present. The most recognized basic CALL study in North America was introduced as a portion of a bigger computer-assisted teaching study at Stanford University in the Institute for Mathematical Studies in the Social Sciences guided by Richard Atkinson and Patrick Suppes (1972). The study started in association with IBM, and after they obtained a subsidy from federal administration funds. In this study, Atkinson observed that learning, as assessed by an exam a week afterward the teaching, might be enhanced meaningfully by including a computer software picks elements for exercise on the foundation of learner’ previous record of accomplishment and element complexity.

The applicability and effectiveness of computer implementation were perceived as crucial by tutors who were benefitting the exclusive mainframe computer period. For instance, Decker (1976) defined his inventive attitude, which included possessing the

computer to demonstrate how to make specific syntactic processes on French learners' sentences. Holmes and Kidd (1982) decided that CALL of this period was comprehended as an addition to classroom teaching instead of as a spare. Several programs around the world searched methods in which instructional objectives could be achieved more resourcefully by way of the implementation of the computer.

Computers turned into commonly accessible to language instructors in the early 1980s. As microcomputers did not necessitate users to be connected to a mainframe computer preserved by a campus or corporation, any educational division, language institute, or unique instructor could obtain one and discover its abilities for language education. Throughout this era, the major action sustained to remain in CALL (Chapelle, 2001, pp. 7–8). The early 1980s was a dynamic period in the advancement of CALL owing to the variety of thoughts suggested and the increasing specialized conversation. This advancement, yet, was tied with the relapse characteristic in a situation apart from what had arisen previously. Regardless of the specialized reflectivity of The CALL in the communicative method, countless CALL creators and users throughout this age seemed to be reinventing the CALL of the 1970s instead of developing on knowledge.

The obstructions occasioning from limits of premature microcomputers were brief as a consequence of quick improvements through the 1980s. During the period, reasonably priced technologies arrived capable of with more and more memory, as well as abilities for audial, visuals and audiovisual. It came to be obvious to numerous people that computers were directed to obtain a lasting position in language education and study. By the late 1980s, CALL had advanced within several determined schemes, specialized organizations containing instructor training, and more precise conduct of assessment matters (Chapelle, 2001, pp. 11–15).

2.2. Computer Simulation Games

In the 80s and 90s, personal computer (PC) gaming was a new area that contained simple features in games such as basic graphics or text-based graphics, commonly basic mono sounds, very basic or without artificial intelligence (A.I.), and non-friendly controls. But now, it has been developed and evolved into a very complex system that contains ultra-realistic graphics and artificial intelligence.

A simulation game is generally designed to simulate real-world activities. Most simulation games have no defined goals or achievements, thus the player is free to control a character or an environment. It can be said that the history of simulation games started with PC games on sports subjects including BMX Simulator (1986), Grand Prix Simulator (1986), and Pro Boxing Simulator (1988) by Code Masters and Oliver. Following these developments of PC games, the first detailed multimedia life simulation game, The Sims has been developed by Maxis and published by Electronic Arts in 2000. Enhancements that simulation games provide in teaching have been researching subjects by many researchers (Saunders, 1999). The Sims takes place in an ordinary environment that reflects the lives of ordinary people and changed the boundaries of gaming by making it realistic as it is in books and movies (Seabrook, 2002). This realism may enhance learners to become involved in the game and interact as if it is a part of the real-life of the United States of America. Yet, the cultural background of learners may affect the acceptance of the game due to the differences between the cultures.

2.3. Theoretical Background on Games for Learning

Piaget (1952) suggested that play and imitation are two important factors in a children's cognitive enhancement process. Plenty of studies on games with adults and children in psychology, education, and anthropology demonstrated that games are crucial conciliators for learning and adjusting into the community (Csikszentmihalyi, 2012; Provost, 2000).

Researchers who further developed Situated Learning Theory mentioned the role of securing learning in authentic situations (Brown, Collins, & Duguid, 2005). One advantage is guiding learners to become connected by the material, thus learners may have metacognitively guided treatments. Learning is meaningful when it is supported with simulated visualization, problem-solving activities and instant feedback with an active learner, thus expired activities such as classroom worksheets may not be efficient in learning (Salomon, Perkins, & Globerson, 1991). Life simulation computer games provide the most opportunities that life includes. These may be both positive and negative content for it. Life simulation computer games deliver problems as people encounter in real life. Additionally, a long-term study with active students may help students since they will get instant feedback on their right and wrong steps.

2.3.1. Input Hypothesis

The hypothesis set main importance on the comprehensible input (CI) that language learners are exposed to. Understanding the inputs of verbal and written language are perceived as the lone instrument that increases underlying linguistic ability, and linguistic production is not understood as having any outcome on learners' aptitude. Additionally, Krashen (1985) claimed that language capability is only progressive when language is subconsciously acquired and that aware learning cannot be used as a basis of spontaneous language production. Thus, life simulation computer games may be appropriate for offering learners a setting where they can acquire new words subconsciously.

2.3.2. Interaction Hypothesis

According to Long (1985), interaction and input are important elements in the language acquisition procedure. He claims that interaction and conversation are the foundation for the progress of language rules by leaving behind the old approach which is based on drilling grammatical structures. Additionally, he suggested that the efficiency of comprehensible input is significantly improved when pupils have to collaborate for meaning. One of the members in a dialogue may tell something which the other member does not comprehend; subsequently, the members can apply several communicative strategies to support communication improvement. The communicative tactics applied in the case can involve talking more carefully, reducing the speed of speech, demands for explaining or restatements (Brown, 2000, pp. 287-288). In a laboratory setting where computers are aligned side by side, learners may communicate with each other for comprehending a new word via playing a game.

2.3.3. Motivation

Gardner, Lalonde, and Moorcroft (1985) described as the degree one's attempt to obtain the language due to the wish to do so and the contentment resulting from it. Motivation is reflected important for its position in language learning achievement. In their socio-educational model, Gardner, Allen and Lambert (1974) state that motivation is based on three elements: effort, desire and affect. Effort discusses the period devoted to exploring the language and the determination of the learner. Desire implies how

much the learner requests to turn out to be competent in the language and affect suggests the learner's emotional feedbacks associated with language learning.

Harmer (1991, p. 3) defines the connotation of motivation as the "internal drive" that drives someone to do something. When we reflect our objective is worthy enough to accomplish, then we attempt to reach that objective; this is described "the action driven by motivation."

Rose, Lightbown, and Spada (2006) mark that motivation in second language learning is utterly complex for studies, yet it can be clarified with two factors: learner's communicative requirements and their approaches regarding the second language community. Moreover, Parsons, Hinson, and Brown (2001) state motivation as a vital element or aspect in the learning process. Learning and motivation partake equal significance to accomplish something. Through motivation, we are stimulated to be successful in the learning process, and learning makes us acquire new information and skills.

According to Gardner (2007), there are two kinds of motivation: language learning motivation and classroom learning motivation. Language learning motivation is an overall and constant characteristic of a learner to learn the language. Classroom learning motivation is the motivation in classroom situations or any explicit condition. The focus is on the perspective of the learner for a task assigned to him/her. This kind of motivation is open to be influenced by plenty of factors such as the teacher, the class atmosphere, the course content, materials and facilities, and personal traits of the learner.

Harmer (1991, p. 3) classify the motivation in second language learning into two types:

- a. *Short-term goal* suggests when pupils desire to thrive in doing something soon, for instance, students who want to pass their English exams.
- b. *Long-term goal* relates to the aspiration of pupils or learners who aim to get better jobs in the future or to be able to communicate with individuals who use the target language.

Krashen (1988, p. 22) mentioned the following factors that affect language learning in terms of motivation:

- a. *Integrative motivation* outlined as the craving to be an element of renowned or significant members of the community or the society which converse in the

second language. It is grounded on the curiosity in learning the second language due to learners' demand to connect or socialize with the individuals who use the second language or because of the purpose to join the community. Sometimes it includes feeling or emotional aspects (Saville-Troike, 2012).

- b. *Instrumental motivation* involves the notions of solely pragmatic usefulness in learning the second language to raise the occasions for learners' vocations or concerns, give learners further respect and influence, gain access to specialized and scientific data, or merely succeeding in a course in school (Saville-Troike, 2012).

Additionally, motivation is grouped into two core classes as in the following:

- a. *Intrinsic motivation* states that learning by self while having own reward. This signifies that learners are eagerly and gladly attempt to learn for which they consider it is worthy or significant for them. Once pupils have intrinsic motivation, they have an interior wish to learn and they do not have the necessity for exterior effects. There are no harmful influences on having intrinsic motivation. Additionally, intrinsic motivation impulses pupils to learn without prizes, since the necessity is inborn or emerge from inside or be subject to their determinations. In *How Languages Are Learned* (Rose et al., 1995) it is cited that educators do not have many influences on pupils' intrinsic motivation since pupils are from diverse conditions and the only method to stimulate pupils is by arranging the classroom in a helpful setting.
- b. *Extrinsic motivation* mentions having a wish to get a prize and evade punishment. It highlights the exterior necessity to convince the learner to participate in a learning activity (Mora & Arnold, 2000), for instance, homework, marks, or performing something to gratify instructors. Mutually integrative and instrumental motivations are sorted under the division of extrinsic motivation (Hedge, 2003). As extrinsic motivation is founded on exterior effects such as prizes and punishment, this kind of motivation possibly will carry an undesirable influence to pupils, because through extrinsic motivation, pupils do not acquire with their resilient intent or drive but they learn since they are boosted by the attention in the prizes or the punishment. The minute a learner learns as the learner is promised prizes or because he requests

the prizes, the learner will be exceedingly driven to attend to lessons and learn and accomplish the objective that is fixed for the learner. Nevertheless, once these prizes are withdrawn, or occasionally though the learner does not get any punishment, the learner will not be attracted in attending to lessons and learn the language.

Finally, learning a language involves a significant determination. Individuals study a language for various motives: A desire to become like the natives of the language (integrative motivation) is frequently a solid encouraging aspect for young learners, however, the usefulness of what is achieved by learning (instrumental motivation) is usually a deeper stimulus for adults. Additionally, motivation may arise from the wish of learning (intrinsic motivation). Subsequently, enhancing motivation and the period pupils devote exercising is vital for an effective CALL implementation. Game creators concentrate on discovering methods to hold the players attracted. For this objective, they formed numerous efficient projects to gain and hold players attracted and motivated while playing a game. This is called as successful gameplay. According to Prensky (2002), gameplay is the entire actions, considering and choice selection that brands a game either entertaining or not. Without addiction, there is no good gameplay and what causes masses of individuals to devote a noteworthy extent of their time and capital to playing games. The enjoyment of attachment is the motivation to play. Thus, game type and content may play a role in motivating learners.

2.3.4. Schema Theory

Schema Theory is a cognitive learning theory used by psychologists, linguists, and psycholinguistics, to understand better the process of comprehension. It was introduced by psychologist Sir Fredric Bartlett (Saito, 2003), made popular by another psychologist Jean Piaget (McLeod, 2015), and later expanded on by education psychologist Richard Anderson (Anderson & Pearson, 2016). Schema Theory suggests that all knowledge is organized into units. It is a mental framework that people use to represent and organize stored knowledge. Schemata are the building blocks of cognition, and they present our unique view pulled from our personal experiences and prior knowledge of things.

Some studies on recycling (Hwang & Nation, 1989; Sutarsyah, Nation, & Kennedy, 1994) demonstrate that reading-related stories are useful for avoiding vocabulary load. Thus, simulation games may be useful since they are based on a few topics. More specifically, multimedia life simulation games are based around daily life vocabulary context. Therefore, this type of game can be used as teaching materials for vocabulary. The game instrument in this study is based on categories and sub-categories. Thus, encountering words in an organized system may activate their schemata and help them to acquire.

2.3.5. Cognitive Information Processing Theories and Models

Information processing is an area with plenty of different theories, hypotheses, and models. Cognitive studies (Anderson, 1992; Atkinson & Shiffrin, 2016; McLaughlin, Rossman, & McLeod, 1983; Miller, 1956; Schmidt, 1990) implies that human brain is a hard drive as of a computer with intelligence, attention, motivation, mind, and senses.

2.3.5.1. Information Processing Theory

Information Processing Theory (Miller, 1956) claims that fresh information should be processed in the active memory to build schemata in long-term memory. This theory implicates that the human mind is a kind of computer or a processor. According to him, when a new input is gathered and stored in short-term storage, it is processed in the brain and finally, the brain may be able to produce. In this perspective, multimedia information provided by computer games helps to address most senses while learners actively participate in the learning process. Thus, the schemata can be accessed with plenty of ways via computer games.

2.3.5.2. Attention-Processing Model

According to McLaughlin, Rossman, and McLeod (1983), language learning is a process from the control mechanism to automatic processing. It starts with all controlled system, through time and experience, it becomes automatic. When it becomes automatic, it is called learning. The model classes its linking of the mind and computer by expressing that language learning necessitates brain processing to learn, comparable to the processing that occurs inside a computer. The two sorts of processing are

controlled processing (short term memory) and **automated processing** (long term memory) (McLaughlin et al., 1983; Miller, 1956).

Controlled processes are recent skills in which simply a few basics of the skill can be engaged. For instance, when you first learn to type on a keyboard, you may only manage a few elements such as finding where the key you required is, typing with only one finger at a time or typing a wrong letter but do not know how to erase. Everything else regarding the keyboard is exceedingly complicated for your capacity-limited aptitude.

In contrast, automatic processes denote processing in a further proficient skill, where the memory of your brain can cope with extraordinary numbers of bits of data at the same time. The automating of this variety of information is achieved by a procedure of **restructuring** (McLeod & McLaughlin, 1986) in which “the components of a task are coordinated, integrated, or reorganized into new units, thereby allowing the old components to be replaced by a more efficient procedure” (McLaughlin, 1990, p. 118).

In controlled processes, our attention is generally **focal** that is focusing our attention on the central activity, on the other hand, **peripheral** attentions focusing our attention on the edge. For instance, an experienced pianist may not have to focus on the keys while playing (peripheral), yet a beginner pianist ought to focus his/her attention on the keys while even practicing an easy music sheet (focal). Nevertheless, an experienced pianist who plays piano in a concert hall may focally pay attention. Furthermore, in some tasks, there may be a need for consciousness in both focal and peripheral attention. For instance, while someone is driving a car, the focal attention may focus directly on cars ahead, yet the peripheral attention to vehicles behind and alongside, to possible threats and other thoughts. Thus, it is a mistaken thought that evaluating focal attention as conscious attention (Hulstijn, 1990).

2.3.5.3. Adaptive Control of Thought (ACT)

John Robert Anderson (Anderson, 1992) suggested that in controlled processing, our short-term memory is very active and after processing, it sends the necessary data into long term memory. To explain this process, Anderson came up with two types of knowledge: Declarative and Procedural Knowledge. Declarative knowledge is related to know the rule while the other is to know how to use the rule. Declarative knowledge consisting of facts such as Ankara is the capital city of Turkey, “ $5 + 5 = 10$ ”, or “Alpha”

is the first letter of the Greek alphabet. On the other hand, procedural knowledge is about productions. Productions are representations of knowledge about how we act: for instance, knowledge about how to open a bottle, how to ride a bike or how to create a robot. According to Adaptive Control of Thought (ACT), all information starts as declaratory data; procedural information is learned by making implications from previously standing accurate information. According to Anderson, the move from declarative to procedural knowledge takes place in three stages: **cognitive** (explicit learning), **associative** (practice) and **autonomous** stages (use).

2.3.5.4. Multi-Store Model

Atkinson and Shiffrin (1968) claimed that memory works in a linear line and it has three parts: a sensory memory, short-term memory, and long-term memory. Information starts its journey by sense organs and perceived into sensory memory. According to this model, unrepeated information will not be able to make its way from short-term memory into long-term memory.

Each part of the memory has three characteristics: encoding, capacity, and duration. Encoding is the method of how we can process new information into a new element to contain it in memory. In our memory, the main encoding processes are visual, acoustic and semantic. Capacity includes concerns of how many data can be recorded, and duration is the time of the data before they are eliminated from the memory.

2.3.6. Noticing Hypothesis

The Noticing Hypothesis is a notion in second-language acquisition suggested by Richard Schmidt (1990). He declared that learners cannot acquire the linguistic characteristics or lexis of a language unless they notice them. Noticing unaided does not indicate that learners consequentially acquire language; relatively, the hypothesis states that noticing is the vital preliminary goal for acquisition. There is discussion over whether learners should intentionally notice something, or whether the noticing can be subliminal to some step. A simulation game that includes words in many areas can help students to notice the words which they have not encountered before or that they have not noticed. In particular, applications that involve interaction and in which certain

stages for progress in the game are not able to be reached without apprehending can enable students to understand the words and their uses.

2.3.7. Autonomy

Holec (1981) described the autonomy of learner as the responsible movement of learners for themselves. On every occasion self-governing education is being explored, the culture of that learning context should be taken into account. Social scientists approve that it is not possible to create a culture-free education setting (Surma, 2004). In spite of this harmony, the concept of learner autonomy has been identified mainly by considerations extended from the Western world. Jones (1995) notified that if autonomy is comprehended as a universal term, it causes a risk since the explanation of autonomy maybe determined by culture. As Surma (2004) indicated the importance of that settings are unique and they may occur in a similar culture and the settings created for a culture are not able be global. Background diversity usually arises because of personal instructor variances inside a culture or institute. Furthermore, it is vital to organize the plans and strategies according to the backgrounds of the learners. When diversity among the students is high, then unacceptability of the methods may take place.

In English classrooms of universities in Turkey, it is common to observe a cultural diversity. Especially in the provinces located in the south of the country, there has been an intercultural cultural difference due to the recent unfortunate events, as well as a domestic cultural difference. Therefore, it is very difficult to evaluate the concept of autonomy on an individual basis. Nevertheless, although autonomy varies across cultures, it is an important concept for students to discover what they can do and to notice new information they encounter. Open world sandbox computer games give quite a lot of freedom in this respect. This freedom also carries autonomy and provides students with methods for discoveries. Although student autonomy is not a well-established concept due to cultural characteristics in Turkey, it is a concept that needs to be integrated into education in order to create academic awareness among students.

2.4. Teaching Vocabulary

Vocabulary teaching started with repeating strategies and focused on finding how much practice is needed to learn a wordlist or adjusting the correct timeline between the repetitions (Crothers & Suppes, 1967). Yet, studies demonstrated to us that

rote repetition is not efficient enough (Atkinson & Raugh, 1975). Research on this issue continued with the “keyword” method, which is finding a word in the first language that is pronounced like a second language word, then connecting the keyword with the second language word via an image. Even though solid evidence appears on its efficiency over other strategies (Cohen, 1987), Meara (1980) mentioned that these kinds of studies ignore the complexity of meaning relationships that are required to complete a proper lexicon.

Most research before the 1990s disregards second language learners’ need of threshold-level second language skill that is one of the important features of second language learners which differs them from first language learners. Without this, pure wordlists are useless (Gu, 1994). To overcome this issue, research on acquiring vocabulary through meaningful reading became popular (Waring & Nation, 2004). Furthermore, foreign language words cannot be just evaluated with their referential meaning but syntactic, pragmatic, and even emotional transfer in a context should be considered as a whole with the words.

2.4.1. Studies on Vocabulary Teaching via Computer Games

In a study using the Sims in 2015 (Noroozloo et al.), they researched 60 participants in two groups (control and experiment group) and the results demonstrated that there was a significant difference between the control group and the experiment group. The study indicated that computer games may be decent sources for vocabulary learning, and they can provide incidental vocabulary learning context by creating a meaningful and enjoyable setting.

Ranalli (2008) suggested that commercially created computer games may be modified for learners with the assistance of supplementary vocabulary learning documents. Furthermore, he concluded that the Sims is theoretically popular among English as a Second Language learners.

Another study (Miller & Hegelheimer, 2006) using the Sims as the basis implied that the game helped students in mostly vocabulary acquisition. Yet, the Sims is very close relationships with culture. They conclude that since the game may seem based on capitalistic objectives and regular habits of the characters, the approval of the game may change according to learners’ cultural background.

CHAPTER III

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Introduction

This study is designed as the Nonequivalent Groups Design with the support of journals kept by the researcher and the opinions of the lecturer of the classes. This research is a mixed-type study to reveal the effects of multimedia life simulation games and the positive and the negative outcomes of using multimedia life simulation games in vocabulary learning of English language learners who are in prep classes of Mustafa Kemal University, Hatay.

3.2. Research design

Among the quantitative experimental research methods, the Nonequivalent Groups Design was used in this study to describe the effects of life simulation games -in our case, the Sims 4 -in vocabulary learning by an experimental study. In this design, there was a control group and an experiment group. Both groups got pretest and posttest to compare the results but only the experiment group got treated. The main aim of this type of design is to find out whether the experiment group improves more than the participants who are in the control group (Price, Jhangiani, Chiang, Leighton, & Cuttler, n.d.).

3.3. Variables

The independent variable in this study is going to be a multimedia life simulation game. On the other hand, the dependent is the vocabulary size of the students over time.

3.4. Participants

The participants in this study were 18 undergraduate students from two prep classes at Mustafa Kemal University, Hatay. The number of participants in the experiment group was nine while the others were in the control group. The participants were selected by their convenience and the opinions of the lecturer of the preparation

class for creating two similar groups. All participants in this study were between 18- and 20-years old students and gender differences were disregarded.

3.5. Analysis

The quantitative data were compiled into SPSS to calculate descriptive statistics, Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test and Mann-Whitney U Test values for the pretest, posttest and questionnaire data. The qualitative data from the open-ended questions from the implementation evaluation questionnaire and the journal entries written by the researcher were thematically coded by identifying utterances that revealed attitudinal or motivational characteristics.

3.6. Instruments

In this research, there were four instruments: pretest, posttest, a multimedia life simulation game, journal entries, and an implementation evaluation questionnaire. Instruments were chosen by applicability and limitations.

3.6.1. Pretest and Posttest

Both pretest and posttest instruments were the same and there were 49 questions totally which are 28 multiple-choice, 15 matching and 6 cloze questions. The questions were prepared with the help of Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English Online (Procter, 1978) for word meanings and corpus scanning. These tests are to measure written receptive vocabulary knowledge required for reading. Written and oral explanations were made in the participants' native languages. The posttest was handed out to the participants six weeks later after the pretest.

3.6.2. A Multimedia Life Simulation Game

As the multimedia life simulation game, The Sims 4 was chosen since it is the most generic and user-friendly game in multimedia life simulation category in computer games. The Sims 4 is a multimedia life simulation computer game which contains life content. In the Sims 4, players can create families, and lead the families and characters (called as Sims in the Sims 4) through the difficulties they encounter in everyday life (Maxis, 2014). Players care about the needs of their Sims such as physical and

emotional needs. Additionally, players also find them jobs, solve their problems, build homes including furniture and appliances, improve their skills, raise children, celebrate holidays and so forth. Even though the game does not contain any verbal English content except some music pieces, it offers a wide deal of vocabulary content in every aspect of the game. The emotions in the game affect Sims' social interactions and create a context for each conversation with another Sim or Sims. These conversations do not include phrasal structure but only a word-based one- or two-words style.

3.6.3. Journal Entries

The researcher kept a journal to be able to evaluate the process qualitatively. These journal entries helped the researcher to understand that whether the participants grasp the meanings of the words in the game or they purely understand the mechanics of the game and play with this information without trying to get the meaning by only click-gaming.

3.6.4. Implementation Evaluation Questionnaire

Collecting feedback from the experimental group was important to evaluate the data qualitatively and quantitatively. This instrument contains 33 5-Likert scale questions and three open-ended questions. The questionnaire was only given to the experiment group and in their native language for avoiding incomprehensibility.

3.7. Procedural Details

This experimental research was conducted in Mustafa Kemal University Tayfur Sökmen Campus, Faculty of Education and Faculty of Science and Literature, Hatay, Turkey. In each week, the participants joined the Sims 4 session for two hours for four weeks. The participants had the chance to access to Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English Online (Procter, 1978) via their computer. Table 1 demonstrates the procedure for the Sims 4 sessions.

Table 1.

Procedural Schedule for Implementation

Schedule	Tasks	Objectives
Week 1	This week, the participants	to use or identify the
a) Getting used to the mechanics of the implementation	start the game and create their characters with various personality and appearance features. After the character creation step, the characters start with 20,000 Simoleons and buy a house on the map. While getting used to the mechanics with the help of the in-game tutorial, the participants should also satisfy the needs of the Sims they created.	words below. Trait Active Ambitious Cheerful Clumsy Creative Erratic Foodie Geek Genius Gloomy Glutton Self-assured
Week 2	In the second week, the participants focus on getting a job or career and accumulating 10,000 simoleons for building a new house. While creating capital social interactions with Non-player Sims are necessary. There should be at least three relationships. These social interactions should include friendly, meanly and romantic approaches.	to use or identify the words and chunks below. Friendly Interactions Admire Apologize Deep in conversation Get to know Gossip Impress Mean Interactions Argue Attack

		Beat up
		Break up
		Enemy
		Insult
		Mock
		Prank
		Scare

Week III	In the third week, the	to use or identify the
a) Selecting a hobby and increasing skills	participants focus on	words below.
b) Designing a house	buying objects, being	
c) Buying objects in Build Mode	interested in a hobby by	Buy Mode
	making its level at least 5	Bathtub
	and designing a new house	Ceiling
	after bulldozing the	Counter
	former. The house should	Display
	include a kitchen,	Dresser
	bedroom, study room,	Lighting
	living room, and	Oven
	bathroom.	Plumbing
	The kitchen should	Sculpture
	contain 1 refrigerator, 1	Shower
	oven, 4 counters, 1 sink	Sink
	for the counter, 1 trash	Stove
	can, and 2 ceiling lamps.	
	The bedroom should	Skills
	contain 1 double-sized	Baking
	bed, 2 end tables, 1	Gardening
	dresser, and 1 ceiling	Handiness
	lamp.	Logic
	The study room should	Mischief
	contain 1 study desk, 1	Mixology
	chair, 1 ceiling lamp, 1	Violin
	rug, 1 computer, 1 hobby	Wellness

item, and 1 bookcase or 1 bookshelf.

The living room should contain 1 sofa, 1 couch, 1 coffee table, 1 television, 1 floor lamp, 2 miscellaneous decorations, 1 dinner table, 2 chairs, and 1 ceiling lamp.

The bathroom should contain 1 sink, 1 shower, 1 rug, 1 toilet, and 2 wall lamps.

Week IV

<p>a) Having a baby</p> <p>b) Attending the baby's requirements</p> <p>c) Getting promoted</p> <p>d) Decorating the house</p> <p>e) Starting the gardening hobby</p>	<p>In the last week, the participants focus on having babies, help them to grow up healthily, getting promoted to at least level 6 of their careers or jobs, decorating the houses with at least 10 decoration items, and starting the gardening hobby by creating a little garden.</p>	<p>to use or identify the words below, and use or identify the words and chunks encountered at the previous weeks.</p> <p>Seed</p> <p>Herb</p> <p>Vegetable</p> <p>Plant</p> <p>Fertilize</p> <p>Grow</p>
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CHAPTER IV

4. FINDINGS

4.1. Introduction

This chapter is focused on demonstrating collected data and the data's analyses via SPSS (version 26) and thematic coding. This chapter contains two sections: Data Analyses of SPSS Results (section 4.2.), and Questionnaire and Journal Entries (section 4.3.)

4.2. Data Analyses of SPSS Results

Table 2.

Average pretest results of the groups

	Group	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
Pretest	Experiment	9	20.78	6.220
	Control	9	18.78	2.224

According to Table 2, the experiment group got slightly higher scores on the mean (20.78) than the control group (18.78). Additionally, the range for scores in the experiment group is higher (6.220).

Table 3.

Average posttest results of the groups

	Group	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
Posttest	Experiment	9	25.78	6.140
	Control	9	20.00	1.936

According to Table 3, the experiment group got higher scores on the mean (25.78) than the control group (20.00). Compared to Table 2, both groups increased their scores.

Table 4.
Descriptive Statistics for the Experiment Group

	N	Mean	Minimum	Maximum
Pretest	9	20.78	10	29
Posttest	9	25.78	14	32

Table 4 indicated that while the minimum score of the experiment group in pretest was 10, it was 14 in the posttest; and while the maximum score was 29 in the pretest, it was 32 in the posttest. The table demonstrates that the mean in the pretest was 20.78 and it changed into 25.78 in the posttest.

Table 5.
Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test for the Experiment Group

		N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Z	Sig.
Pretest	- Negative Ranks	2 ^a	1.75	3.50	-2.255 ^c	.024
Posttest	Positive Ranks	7 ^b	5.93	41.50		

a. Pretest > Posttest b. Pretest < Posttest c. Based on negative ranks.

According to Table 5, seven persons got higher scores in the posttest than the pretest while two persons got lower scores in the posttest than the pretest. $Z = -2.255$ and based on negative ranks. The table indicates that there is a meaningful difference ($p = .024$, $p < .05$) between the scores of the pretest and posttest.

Table 6.
Descriptive Statistics for the Control Group

	N	Mean	Minimum	Maximum
Pretest	9	18.78	15	23
Posttest	9	20.00	17	22

Table 6 indicated that while the minimum score of the control group in pretest was 15, it was 17 in the posttest; and while the maximum score was 23 in the pretest, it was 22 in the posttest. The table demonstrates that the mean in the pretest was 18.78 and it changed into 20.00 in the posttest.

Table 7.

Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test for the Control Group

		N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Z	Sig.
Pretest	- Negative Ranks	2 ^a	3.00	6.00	-1.997 ^c	0.046
Posttest	Positive Ranks	7 ^b	5.57	39.00		

a. Pretest > Posttest b. Pretest < Posttest c. Based on negative ranks.

According to Table 7, seven persons got higher scores in the posttest than the pretest while two persons got lower scores in the posttest than the pretest. $Z = -2.255$ and based on negative ranks. The table indicates that there is a meaningful difference ($p = 0.046$, $p < 0.05$) between the scores of the pretest and posttest.

Table 8.

Mann –Whitney Test Analysis for Both Groups

	Group	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
Pretest	Experiment	9	10.44	94.00
	Control	9	8.56	77.00
Posttest	Experiment	9	12.50	112.50
	Control	9	6.50	58.50

When Table 8 is interpreted, it can be claimed that the experiment group increased its ranks sum from 94.00 (the pretest) to 112.50 (the posttest). On the other hand, the control group decreased its ranks sum from 77.00 (the pretest) to 58.50 (the posttest). According to Table 5 and Table 7, both groups increased their scores significantly. Yet, a higher sum of ranks difference means a higher increase in the scores were provided by the group, in this case, the experiment group.

Table 9.

Mann – Whitney Test Statistics for both Groups

	Z	Significance
Pretest	-0.755	0.489
Posttest	-2.404	0.014

Table 9 indicates that in the pretest there were no significance difference ($p = 0.489$, $Z = -0.755$) between the experiment and the control group but there is a significant difference ($p = 0.014$, $p < 0.05$, $Z = -2.404$) between the experiment and the control group.

4.3. Questionnaire and Journal Entries

Table 10.

Thematic Categories for the answers of Q34

	Frequency	Percent
Game type	5	55.6
Abundance of visuals	3	33.3
Lack of time	1	11.1
Total	9	100.0

In Table 10, according to the thematical categories of open-ended questionnaire question (Q) 34 which asked “What kind of changes should be made for the study to be beneficial to the students?” more than half of the participants (55.6%) thought that a different kind of game would be more helpful for learning vocabulary. Additionally, the researcher highlighted this datum in his journal by stating:

Most of the participants could not understand the mechanics of the game since it is an open world sandbox game based on life simulation which can offer endless opportunities. The main problem was that most of the students did not have any computer game experience. Thus, the participants got bored since they got stuck.

Table 11.

Descriptive Analysis for Questionnaire Question 14

	Frequency	Percent
Disagree	1	11.1
Neutral	1	11.1
Agree	2	22.2
Totally Agree	5	55.6
Total	9	100.0

According to Table 11, most of the participants (77.8%) think that new words can be learned via computer games. In addition to these data, for Q2, all of the participants (9) agreed that if the study develops, it can be helpful for English vocabulary acquisition.

In comparison with the results of Q14 (see Table 10), Q34 and Q2, most of the participants thought that this study may be meaningful for vocabulary acquisition but the game may not be appropriate.

Table 12.

Descriptive Analysis for Questionnaire Question 16

	Frequency	Percent
Neutral	1	11.1
Agree	4	44.4
Totally Agree	4	44.4
Total	9	100.0

Nearly all (88.8%, see Table 12) of the students believed that they focused on the visual content more than the written content. Furthermore, in open-ended Q34, this opinion was stated by the participants (44.4%) was to reduce the visual abundance and increase the frequency of the words in the game.

Table 13.

Descriptive Analysis for Questionnaire Question 13

	Frequency	Percent
Totally Disagree	3	33.3
Disagree	2	22.2
Agree	1	11.1
Totally Agree	3	33.3
Total	9	100.0

Table 13 demonstrates that only four of the participants thought that they have adequate information and experience for computer games. The rest claimed that they do not have necessary information and experience for computer games.

Table 14.

Descriptive Analysis for Questionnaire Question 17

	Frequency	Percent
Totally Disagree	2	22.2
Disagree	1	11.1
Neutral	2	22.2
Agree	2	22.2
Totally Agree	2	22.2
Total	9	100.0

According to Table 14, three participants stated that the game was interesting for them. In the comparison of the data of Q13, Q17, and Q34, it can be implied that the ones who have knowledge and experience in computer games mostly liked the game. For this matter, the researcher stated in the journals:

The participants who do not know what to do started to click-gaming. They focused on the visual content so much that they disregarded the descriptions provided by the game and the words written on the buttons and asked for assistance from the researcher whenever they got stuck. In conversations among us, I realized that the ones who have problems with playing did not have a computer gaming background.

In addition to previous answers for open-ended Q34, a participant pointed out that time was not adequate for learning this type of game and she had problems with getting used to the mechanics in this short time.

Table 15.

Thematic Categories for the answers of Q35

	Frequency	Percent
Appropriate word amount	5	55,6
Details of the game	3	33,3
Click-gaming	1	11,1

In Q35, it is stated that “What aspects do you find useful for vocabulary learning in the game you play? If there is no direction you find useful, explain why.” Five participants (see Table 15) explained that the game had an abundance of words. One of them indicated “Since the game is consistently given hints or tasks in writing, we become familiar with words, and naturally, it makes learning even easier.” Another participant wrote “To advance in the game we had to learn the meaning of words we do not know. Thus I found it useful.” The third participant who mentioned words expressed herself by saying “Each item I clicked in the game had options and each option was performing a different operation. The game encouraged me to explore the words I didn't know.”

In relation to Table 15, the second mutual opinion for the Q35 was “details of the game” Three participants believed that exceeding visual content made them distracted from words. In the journal entries the researcher stated:

What the participants encountered was freewill. They were not used to be the center of the classroom context. With this study, they became the mediator of what they learn. There were some tasks, yet, their curiosity and decisions were important. Thus, there was not any strict guidance. Consequently, this made them confused.

Additionally, when stated in Q19, “I had times when I did not know what to do.” All of the participants agreed with this statement, and when it is expressed “I did not

know which words I should focus on.” Nearly all of the participants agreed with the statement. The researcher scribed in the journal entries:

They were asking for instruction all the time. Even though I told them in the beginning that they were not going to get complex instructions except assistance for the computers and the game, sometimes they just passed time instead of exploring the game.

Table 16.

Thematic Categories for the answers of Q36

	Frequency	Percent
Games	6	30,0
Movies and series	5	25,0
Speaking practice	5	25,0
Books	4	20,0

According to Table 16, when asked “What are your preferred ways to improve your English vocabulary size?” for Q36, 6 answers included they prefer games for learning English vocabulary, and movies and series (25%) followed this datum by sharing them with speaking practice answers (25%).

CHAPTER V

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

5.1. Introduction

This chapter aims to provide a link between the findings of the research by discussing the matter and finally conclude the study. Additionally, it contains various interpretations as to the extent to which the findings answer the research questions and to what extent contributes to the solution of the statement of the problem section.

5.2. Summary of the Study

This study aimed at finding the results of the effects of a computer multimedia life simulation game implementation in English vocabulary learning, and to investigate the positive and negative aspects of computer multimedia life simulation in a classroom setting. In this study, there were 18 preparatory class students from two different classes and the research was conducted in a computer laboratory at Mustafa Kemal University, Turkey. The data collection instruments in this research were a vocabulary size test which included 28 multiple-choice, 15 matching and 6 cloze questions, an implementation evaluation questionnaire and the journal entries described by the author. The quantitative data were entered into SPSS (version 26) for calculation and the qualitative data were thematically coded and classified.

5.3. The Effectiveness of Computer Multimedia Simulation Games

According to the quantitative results of this study to answer the first research question, it was observed that using simulation games on a task-based origin created a meaningful difference in the English vocabulary of experimental group students. The given tasks included as few instructions as possible to support the autonomy of the students because students needed to focus on the game and adapt to the game internally in order to instinctively adopt the game they use. Since it is not feasible to designate a different game for each student, an inclusive game decision is an important element in regards to the selves of the students as the game may contain content from the interests of the students.

When the shared findings were examined in detail, it was observed that the students did not have enough information about the use of the words since 25 questions of the tests were based on finding the closest meaning. Furthermore, informal interviews with students revealed that they used many similar meaning words. These findings may indicate that learners have not received enough input. In addition, it is thought that the students know only the Turkish translation of the words but do not know their use in English, and a study aimed at correcting these deficiencies is not applied at a sufficient level in the places where the students are educated. Therefore, this study and similar studies may be useful for students to learn about the use of words.

5.4. The Positive and Negative Aspects of Implementation of Simulation Games

For the second research question, it was aimed to determine the positive and negative consequences of using a computer life simulation game in the classroom environment. When the questions in the questionnaire were compared with the open-ended questions and combined with the observer's observations, the positive and negative aspects of using life simulation games emerged to a certain extent.

The students mostly enjoyed playing a simulation game as a different course method. In this way, in a game with a lot of content, encountering words that had never come before the students or they didn't realize the words made the participants see the missing points in terms of their vocabulary size. Moreover, the details provided by the game while processing the life of an ordinary person were stimulating for the students. The content in the game categories, the findings of the students' schemata seems to have activated. With these, when the students were observed, it was comprehensible that they transferred information on the meanings of the words with each other.

The open-world and freedom provided by life simulation games occasionally led students to aimlessly click-gaming. To solve this issue, in addition to the commercial simulation games that have been proven to be beneficial in vocabulary teaching (Miller & Hegelheimer, 2006; Ranalli, 2008; Rankin, Gold, & Gooch, 2006), the production of limited educational simulation games aimed at language teaching, where only the specified words are the main target, can make a significant contribution to the students' focus.

The students also felt that the type of game used was not suitable for them. This problem may be due to the fact that students between the ages of 18 and 20 prefer more

active inputs. In addition, most of the students stated that they did not have a background in computer games before. Therefore, it is quite possible that such an opinion has emerged because they cannot understand the general logic of the games. The game used in implementation can be quite complicated for someone who has just taken a new step in the world of computer games. In addition to having enough input and interaction in the game, students may not have had enough time to notice and examine these inputs.

5.5. Implications for Further Studies

To carry out similar studies with larger sample size is important for obtaining more data. Selecting games with less content and plainer gameplay to prevent participants from getting confused in the game would be more appropriate for participants without game history. Understanding the game's gameplay should also be taken into consideration, and the time of implementation may be extended to develop a more meaningful study. In addition, it may be more effective to include more open-ended questions in surveys that are likely to be used. In similar studies, interviews will also take place, and the data, where participants' ideas can be presented, will provide more information on the positive and negative aspects of using games in the classroom.

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7. APPENDICES

Appendix 1. Ethic Committee Approval of Çağ University

T.C	
ÇAĞ ÜNİVERSİTESİ	
SOSYAL BİLİMLER ENSTİTÜSÜ	
TEZ / ARAŞTIRMA / ANKET / ÇALIŞMA İZİNİ / ETİK KURULU İZİNİ TALEP FORMU VE ONAY TUTANAK FORMU	
ÖĞRENCİ BİLGİLERİ	
T.C. NOSU	30382697154
ADI VE SOYADI	İbrahim Hakkı Ergin
ÖĞRENCİ NO	20178058
TEL. NO.	5348447406
E - MAİL ADRESLERİ	ibrahimergin@icloud.com
ANA BİLİM DALI	İngiliz Dili Eğitimi
HANGİ AŞAMADA OLDUĞU (DERS / TEZ)	Tez
İSTEKDE BULUNDUĞU DÖNEME AİT DÖNEMLIK KAYDININ YAPILIP- YAPILMADIĞI	2019 GÜZ DÖNEMİ KAYDINI YENİLEDİM.
ARAŞTIRMA/ANKET/ÇALIŞMA TALEBİ İLE İLGİLİ BİLGİLER	
TEZİN KONUSU	The Effects of Computer Multimedia Life Simulation Games in English Vocabulary Learning
TEZİN AMACI	Multimedya hayat simülasyonu oyunlarının öğrencilerin İngilizce kelime bilgileri üzerine etkisi olup olmadığını bulmak.
TEZİN TÜRKÇE ÖZETİ	Bu çalışma, multimedya hayat simülasyonu oyunlarının öğrencilerin kelime edinimlerinde bir rol oynayıp oynamadıkları ve bu tür oyunların yeterli etkileşim sağlayıp sağlamadıklarını keşfetmeyi amaçlar.
ARAŞTIRMA YAPILACAK OLAN SEKTÖRLER/ KURUMLARIN ADLARI	Mustafa Kemal Üniversitesi
İZİN ALINACAK OLAN KURUMA AİT BİLGİLER (KURUMUN ADI- ŞUBESİ/ MÜDÜRLÜĞÜ - İLİ - İLÇESİ)	Mustafa Kemal Üniversitesi, Hatay, Antakya.
YAPILMAK İSTENEN ÇALIŞMANIN İZİN ALINMAK İSTENEN KURUMUN HANGİ İLÇELERİNE/ HANGİ KURUMUNA/ HANGİ BÖLÜMÜNDE/ HANGİ İLANINA/ HANGİ KONULARDA/ HANGİ GRUBA/ KİMLERE/ NE YAPILANACAKI GİBİ AYRINTILI BİLGİLER	Mustafa Kemal Üniversitesi eğitim fakültesindeki yabancı diller bölümüne bağlı hazırlık sınıfı öğrencileriyle bilgisayar destekli bir ortamda bir hayat simülasyonu oyunu eğitim amaçlı kullanılacaktır. Mümkünse iki farklı hazırlık sınıfında, mümkün değilse bir hazırlık sınıfındaki iki eşit grup oluşturmak suretiyle kontrol ve deney grubu oluşturmak arzu edilmektedir. Deneysel bu çalışmada, her iki gruba da ön-test ve son-test uygulanacaktır. Ayrıca deney grubunun çalışma süresince günlük (journal) tutması ve çalışmanın sonucunda nitel yorumlamalar için araştırmacıya teslim etmesi beklenmektedir. Araştırmacı çalışmayı 1 ay süreyle, toplamda 16 saat olacak şekilde uygulamayı talep etmekte ve çalışma süresince deney ortamında gözlemci olarak yer almayı arz etmektedir.
UYGULANACAK OLAN ÇALIŞMAYA AİT ANKETLERİN/ ÖLÇEKLERİN BAŞLIKLARI/ HANGİ ANKETLERİN - ÖLÇEKLERİN UYGULANACAĞI YERLER (ANKETLER, ÖLÇEKLER, FORMLAR, ... V.B. GİBİ EVRAKLARIN İSİMLERİYLE BİRLİKTE KAÇ ADET/SAYFA OLDUKLARINA AİT BİLGİLER İLE AYRINTILI YAZILACAKTIRI)	1. Vocabulary Size Test (Ön ve Son Testler İçin) 2. The Sims 4 1. Çalışmadaki ön ve son testler https://my.vocabularysize.com/ adresindeki 140 soruluk çevrimiçi kelime merkezli sorulardır. 2. Çalışmada, The Sims 4 adlı oyun multimedya hayat simülasyonu olarak kullanılacaktır. The Sims 4 oyunu, eğitimsel amaçlarla kullanıma açık olup, herhangi bir izin alınması gerekmemektedir.

ÖĞRENCİNİN ADI - SOYADI İbrahim Hakkı ERGİN		ÖĞRENCİNİN İMZASI: Enstitüde kalan aslı imzalıdır TARİH:11 / 09/ 2019		
TEZ/ ARAŞTIRMA/ANKET/ÇALIŞMA TALEBİ İLE İLGİLİ DEĞERLENDİRME SONUCU				
1. Seçilen konu Bilim ve İş Dünyasına katkı sağlayabilecektir.				
2. Anılan konu İngiliz dili eğitimi bilimleri faaliyet alanı içerisine girmektedir.				
1.TEZ DANIŞMANININ ONAYI	2.TEZ DANIŞMANININ ONAYI (VARSA)	SOSYAL BİLİMLER ENSTİTÜSÜ MÜDÜRÜNÜN ONAYI	A.B.D. BAŞKANININ ONAYI	
Adı - Soyadı: Ali BIÇKI	Adı - Soyadı:	Adı - Soyadı: Murat KOÇ	Adı - Soyadı: Şehnaz ŞAHİNKARAKAŞ	
Unvanı: Dr. Öğr. Üyesi	Unvanı:	Unvanı: Doç. Dr.	Unvanı: Prof. Dr.	
İmzası : Enstitüde kalan aslı imzalıdır	İmzası:	İmzası: Enstitüde kalan aslı imzalıdır	İmzası: Enstitüde kalan aslı imzalıdır	
11.09.2019	... / ... / 20....	11.09.2019	11.09.2019	
ETİK KURULU ASIL ÜYELERİNE AİT BİLGİLER				
Adı - Soyadı: Mustafa BAŞARAN	Adı - Soyadı: Yücel ERTEKİN	Adı - Soyadı: Deniz Aynur GÜLER	Adı - Soyadı: Ali Engin OBA	Adı - Soyadı: Mustafa Tevfik ODMAN
Unvanı : Prof. Dr.	Unvanı : Prof. Dr.	Unvanı: Prof. Dr.	Unvanı : Prof. Dr.	Unvanı: Prof. Dr.
İmzası : Enstitüde kalan aslı imzalıdır	İmzası : Enstitüde kalan aslı imzalıdır	İmzası : Enstitüde kalan aslı imzalıdır	İmzası :	İmzası :
11.09.2019	 / / 20....	29.11.2019	 / / 20....	... / / 20....
Etik Kurulu Jüri Başkanı - Asıl Üye	Etik Kurulu Jüri Asıl Üyesi	Etik Kurulu Jüri Asıl Üyesi	Etik Kurulu Jüri Asıl Üyesi	Etik Kurulu Jüri Asıl Üyesi
OY BİRLİĞİ İLE	☐	Çalışma yapılacak olan tez için uygulayacak olduğu Anketleri/Formları/Ölçekleri Çağ Üniversitesi Etik Kurulu Asıl Jüri Üyelerince İncelenmiş olup, 11 / 09 / 2019 - 28/ 10 / 2019 tarihleri arasında uygulanmak üzere gerekli izin verilmesi taraflarımızca uygundur.		
OY ÇOKLUĞU İLE	☒			
AÇIKLAMA: BU FORM ÖĞRENCİLER TARAFINDAN HAZIRLANDIKTAN SONRA ENSTİTÜ MÜDÜRÜNE ONAYLATILARAK ENSTİTÜ SEKRETERLİĞİNE TESLİM EDİLECEKTİR. YAZININ PUNTOSU İSE 12 (ON İKİ) PUNTO OLACAK ŞEKİLDE YAZILARAK ÇIKTI ALINACAKTIR.				

Appendix 2. Vocabulary Size Test

I. Sorulardaki altı çizili kelimeler hangi şıkta en yakın manada kullanılmışsa onu işaretleyiniz.	
<p>1. Pride seems to be one of our family <u>traits</u>.</p> <p>A) Certain personal <u>features</u> make people more likely to become victims of violent crime.</p> <p>B) Despite its many <u>qualities</u>, the school simply isn't getting results.</p> <p>C) Maybe sports comedy will become his <u>speciality</u>.</p> <p>D) Her female <u>characters</u> often have strong, important relationships with other women.</p> <p>2. My father always led a very <u>active</u> life.</p> <p>A) She took a <u>positive</u> interest in local charities.</p> <p>B) She's over 80, but is still very <u>energetic</u>.</p> <p>C) The volcano became <u>working</u> last year with a series of eruptions.</p> <p>D) The virus is <u>effective</u> even at low temperatures.</p> <p>3. Linda has always been an <u>ambitious</u> and hard-working manager.</p> <p>A) Guy was <u>greedy</u>, amoral, obsessed with power and self-gratification.</p> <p>B) The atmosphere at our school was highly <u>competitive</u>.</p> <p>C) It is unusual for a footballer to be so <u>passionate</u> about playing for his country.</p> <p>D) He's still really <u>enthusiastic</u> about his new job.</p> <p>4. She was a <u>cheerful</u> and agreeable companion.</p> <p>A) After their election victory, party members seemed positively <u>joyful</u>.</p> <p>B) Mike was a <u>happy</u> child and never gave us any trouble at all.</p> <p>C) You'll like Alan - he's really <u>funny</u>.</p> <p>D) The restaurant was large and <u>pleasant</u>.</p>	<p>5. A <u>clumsy</u> waiter spilled wine all over her new skirt.</p> <p>A) I made a few <u>careless</u> mistakes.</p> <p>B) <u>Novice</u> drivers are responsible for a large portion of all accidents.</p> <p>C) <u>Beginners</u> need to ski on easier slopes.</p> <p>D) She felt <u>awkward</u> in her high-heeled shoes.</p> <p>6. You're so <u>creative</u>! I could never make my own clothes.</p> <p>A) He is not a <u>visionary</u>, unlike those coastal intellectuals.</p> <p>B) She has a <u>unique</u> ability of communicate with animals of all kinds.</p> <p>C) The most <u>productive</u> members of staff are rewarded by financial bonuses.</p> <p>D) Their mistake was in putting too much faith in the law and too little in their own ability to be <u>inventive</u>.</p> <p>7. Her behavior was becoming more and more <u>erratic</u>.</p> <p>A) He looked so <u>different</u> that his own daughter didn't recognize him.</p> <p>B) He lived completely alone and had some slightly <u>strange</u> habits.</p> <p>C) I know it sounds <u>insane</u>, but it's true.</p> <p>D) The characters Arden creates are sometimes <u>bizarre</u>.</p> <p>8. Spotting other <u>foodies</u> eating there is a good start.</p> <p>A) She started as a <u>food critic</u> for a local paper.</p> <p>B) I'd probably be a <u>food taster</u> because I like pies!</p> <p>C) Jane used to work as a <u>cook</u> in an Italian restaurant.</p> <p>D) Now <u>gourmets</u> can treat their palates to real Turkish food.</p>

<p>9. I've also been a <u>geek</u> for about 20 years and got this job.</p> <p>A) He was a nice, <u>hard-working</u> boy who would do anything you asked of him. B) The guy's a born <u>loser</u>. C) Matt was a computer <u>nerd</u> in high school. D) Eight <u>gamers</u> can play on a Local Area Network.</p> <p>10. The film reveals Fellini's <u>genius</u>.</p> <p>A) She was a <u>wise</u> old woman, and we all valued her advice. B) She was <u>cunning</u> enough to keep this latest piece of information secret. C) Quinn's a <u>smart</u> guy, but he talks too much. D) The <u>brilliant</u> physicist Paul Dirac first put forward this theory back in 1990.</p> <p>11. He looks somewhat <u>gloomy</u>.</p> <p>A) I was <u>exhausted</u> every day when I first started teaching. B) He was quite <u>depressed</u> and didn't know which way to turn. C) The hotel staff were very <u>friendly</u> and helpful. D) She's still deeply <u>upset</u> about her uncle's death.</p> <p>12. We had salmon to start, followed by a <u>glutton's</u> dessert of crème brûlée.</p> <p>A) They're real <u>gourmets</u> and buy only the best cuts of meat. B) The <u>food tasters</u> were locals. C) Marco's ambition had been to become a <u>chef</u> in one of the big hotels. D) Each restaurant's dream is to have <u>overeaters</u> as customers.</p>	<p>13. A woman's voice came on the line, firm and <u>self-assured</u>.</p> <p>A) It is strange Ben isn't here. He's usually so reliable. B) This means, I think you are competent and <u>credible</u>. C) George was very <u>confident</u> about his abilities as a writer. D) He made a <u>persuasive</u> case for making the changes.</p> <p>14. Sal stood back to <u>admire</u> her work.</p> <p>A) We <u>appreciated</u> the standard of the painting. B) You should be able to <u>evaluate</u> your own work. C) The total value of the paintings is <u>assessed</u> at \$20 million. D) I need one more stamp to <u>complete</u> the set.</p> <p>15. He later <u>apologized</u> for his behavior.</p> <p>A) I was <u>disappointed</u> that we played so well yet still lost. B) I felt <u>ashamed</u> of the things I'd said to him. C) It was probably too late to <u>say sorry</u>, but she would try anyway. D) I <u>regret</u> leaving school so young.</p> <p>16. They were having a <u>deep conversation</u> on astronomy.</p> <p>A) I've had a <u>long chat</u> with Vinnie. B) Before she went to college, her father sat her down for a <u>serious talk</u>. C) None of us ever heard her <u>speak of</u> the war again. D) She made <u>impassioned speeches</u> on civil rights.</p>
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<p>17. It'll take a while for you to <u>get to know</u> everyone.</p> <p>A) Everyone <u>recognized</u> that I had more background and information in these matters. B) You have to <u>gather information</u> for yourself soon enough. C) You have to <u>learn</u> from your mistakes. D) She <u>knows</u> not to tell anyone.</p> <p>18. Annie usually has all the latest <u>gossip</u>.</p> <p>A) According to recent <u>reports</u>, two of the victims are Americans. B) I hope to have some good <u>news</u> for you soon. C) I've heard all sorts of <u>rumors</u> about him and his secretary. D) The tourist office will be able to give you the <u>information</u> you need.</p> <p>19. Steve borrowed his dad's sports car to <u>impress</u> his girlfriend.</p> <p>A) Several factors are likely to <u>influence</u> this decision. B) Her expression did not <u>change</u>, and she answered me calmly. C) His playing is technically brilliant, but it doesn't <u>excite</u> me. D) The death of the child deeply <u>affected</u> both of them.</p> <p>20. Gallacher continued to <u>argue</u> with the referee throughout the game.</p> <p>A) There has been considerable <u>debate</u> about the way forward for education. B) Littman refused to <u>discuss</u> the case publicly. C) We had already <u>talked</u> that <u>over</u>. D) He got into a <u>dispute</u> over a taxi fare.</p>	<p>21. Fong did not suffer a physical <u>attack</u>, but he was humiliated by the three men.</p> <p>A) As a teenager, he was involved in a <u>raid</u> against a village of Omaha Indians. B) Two men <u>assaulted</u> him after he left the bar. C) A second shot <u>hit</u> her in the back. D) He <u>punched</u> me and knocked my teeth out.</p> <p>22. Her boyfriend got drunk and <u>beat her up</u>.</p> <p>A) Be careful you don't <u>hurt</u> anyone with that knife. B) Dad <u>injured</u> his back lifting some heavy boxes. C) She was screaming and <u>punching</u> him with her fists. D) The robbers <u>repeatedly hit</u> him over the head with a baseball bat.</p> <p>23. The couple <u>broke up</u> last year.</p> <p>A) <u>Separate</u> the numbers into four groups. B) He <u>split</u> from his wife last year. C) She <u>divides</u> her time between New York and Paris. D) The firm's staff will <u>shrink</u> to only four people.</p> <p>24. Cats and dogs have always been natural <u>enemies</u>.</p> <p>A) My <u>opponent</u> was much older than I was. B) The two teams have always been <u>rivals</u>. C) But the political field is inscribed with the logic of friend and <u>foe</u>. D) Lydon was openly <u>hostile</u> to any kind of criticism of the project.</p> <p>25. In some cultures, you <u>insult</u> your host if you do not accept their offer of food.</p> <p>A) His remarks deeply <u>offended</u> many Scottish people. B) Her boss <u>humiliated</u> her in front of all her colleagues. C) I had never done him any <u>harm</u>, yet I seemed to be the object of a deliberate campaign. D) His conscience <u>troubled</u> him.</p>
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<p>26. Lillian was openly <u>mocked</u> for her skinny body.</p> <p>A) He looked so funny that we couldn't stop <u>laughing</u>.</p> <p>B) Linda and Christina were <u>giggling</u> at some private joke.</p> <p>C) He felt so ashamed of his weakness, but George didn't <u>ridicule</u> him at all.</p> <p>D) My mother was embarrassed, but I found the situation highly <u>amusing</u>.</p> <p>27. The fire was started as a <u>prank</u>.</p> <p>A) I'm sick of your <u>games</u>.</p> <p>B) Dave's life was a <u>mess</u>.</p> <p>C) He was always telling <u>jokes</u> and making people laugh.</p> <p>D) I'm getting tired of your silly <u>tricks</u>.</p>	<p>28. Loud noises can <u>scare</u> animals or birds.</p> <p>A) She was <u>frightened</u> by the anger in his eyes.</p> <p>B) This study <u>concerns</u> couples' expectations of marriage.</p> <p>C) Some kids will <u>amaze</u> you with what they can do.</p> <p>D) One of Dundee's players was <u>sent off</u> for punching another player.</p>
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<p>II. Cümlelerdeki boşlukları aşağıdaki kelimelerle uygun şekilde doldurunuz.</p> <p>bathtub / ceiling / counter / lighting / oven / jogging / plumbing / sculpture / shower / sink / stove / baking / flower arranging / gardening / logic / mischief / violin / wellness / charisma /</p> <p>a. I love playing with a toy duck in our</p> <p>b. You can't slice tomatoes on the without a cutting board.</p> <p>c. There is a problem with the system, the lamps are not lit.</p> <p>d. It is fun to sing in the because it's good acoustic.</p> <p>e. I forgot the food in the It must be burned.</p> <p>f. You should wash your hands in the after dinner.</p> <p>g. Spiders hanging from the</p> <p>h. This goldenwas made by my grandfather in 1979.</p> <p>i. I put the teapot on the</p> <p>j. All pipes are leaking water. We should consider renovating the</p> <p>k. She played a note on the</p> <p>l. We no longer follow the of one size fits all, like earlier.</p> <p>m. When you come right down to it, stress affects every aspect of</p> <p>n. They installed a wood-fired oven for pizzas.</p> <p>o. For information on organic methods for your backyard, see page 334.</p>
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<p>III. Aşağıdaki cümlelerdeki boşlukları verilen ipuçlarından yardım alarak tamamlayın.</p> <p>a. It's rather early to be sowing carrot s _ _ d s , isn't it?</p> <p>b. We value h _ _ b s for their taste, but we forget that they also have medicinal properties.</p> <p>c. He runs a fruit and _ _ g _ t _ _ l _ _ stall in the market.</p> <p>d. Water the p _ _ n _ twice a week, preferably in the morning.</p> <p>e. You have to f _ r _ _ l _ _ _ your garden.</p> <p>f. These flowers g _ _ w best in the shade.</p>
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Appendix 3. Lesson Evaluation Form

ÇALIŞMA DEĞERLENDİRME ANKETİ

İfadeler	Tamamen Katılıyorum	Katılıyorum	Kararsızım	Katılmıyorum	Hiç Katılmıyorum
1. Çalışmanın İngilizce kelime öğreniminde faydalı olabileceğini düşünüyorum.					
2. Çalışma geliştirilirse İngilizce kelime öğrenimi konusunda faydalı olabilir.					
3. Çalışmanın hedefiyle alakalı olarak yeterli bilgi verildi.					
4. Çalışma bir plana göre ilerledi.					
5. Çalışmanın hedefiyle alakalı olarak yeterli bilgi verildi.					
6. Çalışma uzun vadede faydalı olabilir.					
7. Aynı çalışma başka bir oyunla uygulanabilir.					
8. Çalışmanın seans başına süresi yeterliydi.					
9. Çalışmanın yapıldığı ortam uygundu.					
10. Çalışmanın yapıldığı bilgisayarlar yeterli özelliğe sahipti.					
11. Teknolojik aletleri çok rahat bir şekilde kullanabilirim.					
12. Bilgisayarları çok rahat bir şekilde kullanabilirim.					
13. Bilgisayar oyunlarıyla ilgili yeterince bilgi ve tecrübem var.					
14. Bilgisayar oyunları aracılığıyla yeni kelime öğrenilebileceğini düşünüyorum.					
15. Oyunu kullanırken çok rahattım.					
16. Oyundaki kelimelerden çok görsellere odaklandım.					
17. Oyun ilgimi hiç çekmedi.					
18. Oyunun oynanışını çözmem kısa zamanımı aldı.					
19. Ne yapmam gerektiğini bilmediğim anlar oldu.					
20. Oyun aracılığıyla kelime öğrenimi zevkliydi.					
21. Oyunu oynamam kelime eksiklerimi fark etmemi sağladı.					
22. Oyun yeni kelimeler öğrenmemi teşvik etti.					
23. Bilmediğim kelimelerin anlamlarını sözlük vb. yardımıyla öğrendim.					
24. Bilmediğim kelimelerin anlamlarını araştırmacıya sorarak öğrendim.					
25. Hangi kelimeleri öğrenmeye odaklanmam gerektiğini bilmiyordum.					
26. Oyundaki kelimeler seviyemin üstündeydi.					
27. Oyundaki kelimeler ilgi alanımın dışındaydı.					
28. Yeni bir kelimenin anlamını öğrendiğimde kendi dilime tercüme ettim.					
29. Öğrendiğim yeni kelimeleri kendi dilimde açıklamakta zorlanırım.					
30. Araştırmacı oyunda takıldığım yerlerde yardımcı oldu.					
31. Araştırmacı ne yaptığımı düzenli olarak takip ediyordu.					
32. Araştırmacı oyunla alakalı yeterli bilgi verdi.					
33. Araştırmacı oyunla alakalı konulara hâkimdi.					

Ek yorumlar:

34. Çalışmanın öğrencilere faydalı olabilmesi için ne gibi eklemeler yapılmalı?

35. Oynadığınız oyunda kelime öğrenimi açısından faydalı bulduğunuz yönler nelerdir? Eğer faydalı bulduğunuz bir yön yoksa, neden olmadığını açıklayınız.

36. İngilizce kelime dağarcığınızı geliştirmek için tercih ettiğiniz yöntem/yöntemler nelerdir?

Appendix 4. Consent Form

Çağ Üniversitesi/Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü/İngiliz Dili Eğitimi

Tez: The Effects of Computer Multimedia Life Simulation Games in English Vocabulary Learning

Dr. Ali BIÇKI (Tez Danışmanı)
e-posta: alibicki@gmail.com
İbrahim Hakkı ERGİN (Yüksek Lisans Öğrencisi)
e-posta: ibrahimergin@icloud.com

Giriş

Bu araştırma projesine katılmaya gösterdiğiniz ilgiden dolayı teşekkür ederiz. Bu sayfadaki giridiler size proje hakkında daha fazla bilgi verecektir, böylece bu araştırmaya katılmak isteyip istemediğinize karar verebilirsiniz.

Lütfen bu bilgileri dikkatlice okumak için zaman ayırın. Anlamadığınız veya hakkında daha fazla bilgi edinmek istediğiniz herhangi bir şey hakkında sorular sorabilirsiniz.

Katılımınız gönüllüdür. Katılmak istemiyorsanız katılmak zorunda değilsiniz. Katılmaya başlarsanız, istediğiniz zaman da durdurabilirsiniz.

Çalışma ne hakkında?

Bu araştırma bilgisayar hayat simülasyon oyunları oynamanın İngilizce kelime öğrenimi üzerine etkisi olup olmadığını ortaya çıkarmak için hazırlanmıştır.

Neler yapmam gerekecek?

Bu çalışma 4 hafta boyunca Cuma günleri bilgisayar laboratuvarında 2 saat süreyle çalışmaya katılmayı gerektirmektedir. Ayrıca çalışmadan önce ve sonra kelime dağarcığını ölçmek üzere İngilizce bir test uygulanacaktır. Bunlara ilaveten çalışma sonunda çalışma değerlendirme formunu da doldurmanız beklenmektedir.

Benim hakkımda elde edilen bilgilere ne olacak?

Çalışmada sizden toplanan verilen hiçbir şekilde üçüncü taraflarla paylaşılmayacaktır. Uygulanan araçlardaki verileriniz sadece araştırmacı ve tez danışmanı tarafından görülecek olup, sadece istatistik oluşturmak amaçlı kullanılacaktır.

Daha fazla bilgiyi nereden edinebilirim?

Çalışma hakkında daha fazla bilgi almak için İbrahim Hakkı ERGİN (ibrahimergin@icloud.com) ile irtibata geçebilirsiniz.

Tüm bilgileri okuduğumu ve çalışmaya katılmayı onaylarım.

01/11/2019

İmza:

İsim Soyisim:

Appendix 5. The Institute Implementation Permission

T.C.
ÇAĞ ÜNİVERSİTESİ
ÇAĞ UNIVERSITY

SAYI : 23867972/ 858
KONU: Tez Anket İzini Hakkında

17.09.2019

MUSTAFA KEMAL ÜNİVERSİTESİ
REKTÖRLÜK MAKAMINA
HATAY

İngiliz Dili Eğitimi Tezli Yüksek Lisans Programı öğrencisi olan (20178058 numaralı) **İbrahim Hakkı ERGİN**, “**The Effects of Computer Multimedia life simulation games in english vocabulary learning**” konulu tez çalışmasını Üniversiteniz öğretim elemanı Dr. Öğr. Üyesi Ali BIÇKI’ nin tez danışmanlığında yürütmektedir. Adı geçen öğrenci tez çalışması kapsamında **Üniversiteniz Eğitim Fakültesi Yabancı Diller Bölümü hazırlık sınıfında halen eğitim gören öğrencileri** kapsamak üzere bir anket uygulaması yapmayı planlamaktadır. Tez çalışması kapsamında belirtilen anketin uygulayabilmesi için gerekli iznin verilmesi hususunu bilgilerinize sunarım.

Prof. Dr. Ünal AY
Rektör
İmzası: Enstitüde kalan aslı
İmzalıdır.

EKLERİ: Bir sayfa tez etik kurul izin formu fotokopisi.

A.Yaşar Bayboğan Kampüsü, Adana-Mersin Karayolu 33800 Yenice-Mersin / TÜRKİYE T. +90 (0324) 651 48 00 F. +90 (0324) 651 48 11
www.cag.edu.tr

Appendix 6. MKÜ Implementation Permission

Evrak Tarih ve Sayısı: 11/11/2019-E.65378

T.C.
HATAY MUSTAFA KEMAL ÜNİVERSİTESİ
Eğitim Fakültesi Dekanlığı

Sayı :30013534-105.04.03.07-
Konu :Gerekli İzinlerin Verilmesi
Hk.

YABANCI DİLLER EĞİTİMİ BÖLÜM BAŞKANLIĞINA

İlgi : 08/11/2019 tarihli 67665382-105.04.03.07-65033 sayılı yazı.

Bölümünüz Dr. Öğr. Üyesi Ali BIÇKI'nın 4 hafta süreyle Fakültemiz Bilgisayar Laboratuvarında Cuma günleri 15.00 - 17.00 saatlerinde danışmanı olduğu Çağ Üniversitesi İngiliz Dili Eğitimi Yüksek Lisans öğrencisi İbrahim Hakkı ERGİN'in "The Effects of Computer Multimedia Life Simulation Games in English Vocabulary Learning" başlıklı yüksek lisans tezi için uygulama yapma istemi Dekanlığımızca uygun görülmüştür.

Bilgilerinizi ve gereğini rica ederim.

Prof.Dr. Mehmet TURAN
Dekan V.

DAĞITIM
Yabancı Diller Eğitimi Bölüm Başkanlığı
Sayın Abdulhak KOCA (Bölüm Sekreteri)

Mevcut Elektronik İmzalar
MEHMET TURAN - Eğitim Fakültesi Dekanlığı (Dekan V.) - 11/11/2019

T: 03262456000 F: 03262456005
E-Posta : egitimiletisim@mku.edu.tr Web:
İletişim: Serpil Yılmaz (Dahili: 245 60 06-164 50)

Bu belge 5070 sayılı Elektronik İmza Kanununun 5. Maddesi gereğince güvenli elektronik imza ile imzalanmıştır.

8. BIBLIOGRAPHY

İbrahim H. ERGİN was born in Antakya, Hatay in 1994. After completing his primary education in İnönü Primary School in 2008, he graduated from Nihal-Turgut Anlar Anatolian Teacher High School in 2012.

Starting in 2013, the Republic of Turkey Teaching English at Maltepe University by making the transfer has completed a bachelor's degree in 2016, Mustafa Kemal University. Since 2018, he has been studying for a master's degree in English Language Education at Çağ University.

Besides being a sworn translator and court interpreter expert, he still works as an English teacher in Terzihöyük Secondary School, Reyhanlı, Hatay, TURKEY.

